

Criticizing epistemic injustice: Rewarding effort to compensate for epistemic exclusion

Roberto Ribeiro Baldino, State University of Rio Grande do Sul, ✉ rrbaldino@terra.com.br
Tânia Cristina Baptista Cabral, State University of Rio Grande do Sul

This is a theoretical paper prompted by reflection on practice. In the first part we criticize the notion of epistemic injustice in favor of epistemic exclusion and suggest rewarding effort to compensate for exclusion. In the second part, we briefly describe how we are rewarding effort to understand in our calculus courses. We ground the evaluation of this effort on firm theoretical basis, clearly distinguishing teaching, understanding, and learning. We frame the epistemology of twentieth century mathematics into an attempt to quilt signified and significant together through arbitrary language conventions called definitions. As teacher-researchers, we take our own classrooms as our object of study and ground theory on practice.

Epistemic injustice and mathematics education

In TWG-21 of Pre-CERME12, we reported our experience with calculus courses in the second semester of 2020. We received the suggestion to refer to “Epistemic injustice in mathematics education” (Tanswell & Rittberg, 2020). This we now do.

Epistemic injustice is a concept that made its *debut* in philosophy by the seminal work of Fricker (2007) who also coined the term.¹ Speaking of “injustice” unavoidably brings “victims” to mind. “Injustice” opens the issue of social victimization, discussed in Dolar (2017) and uttered by Žižek² about the METOO movement. Mladen Dolar remarks that the political correctness concern about social victimization is careful in defining a list of victimized minorities such as racial, sexual, religious, etc., but “curiously, the working class, the basis of capitalist exploitation, doesn’t usually feature on this list” (p. 72). Indeed, he remarks, “the cultural and identity struggles inspire so much more passion and engagement than the political and the economic issues” (p. 72). However, this is not a mere curiosity. The apparent critical intentions of concerns about social victimization do not touch on the economic basis of the object of its critique. We go one step further and argue that this is the symptom of what we call *victimization ideology*.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Epistemic_injustice

² https://youtu.be/ai_UAPaoEW4

For the victimization ideology to be operational, the victim has to play its role. As Dolar (2017) remarks, a revolted Arab immigrant is no longer a victim, he becomes a terrorist. A conniving victim is no longer a victim, she becomes an opportunist. Therefore, repression and the Law have to be evoked to keep the victims attached to their roles, so that victimization ideology may display a humanist and charitable face. Here is our point: *victimization ideology functions to hide the fact that economic exclusion continuously produces "victims."* Consideration of economic exclusion would thwart the relief of culpability that victimization ideology is perceived to produce; it would reveal the true source of culpability. We will show how this cover-up of the economy happens in mathematics education.

Justice is not a natural law. Hegel (1991) shows that it is as old as humanity itself and stems from the exchange of commodities. For Marx (1962), Justice belongs to the ideological superstructure of society which, in its turn, depends on the economic infrastructure. Today, the economic infrastructure determines the dominant class almost directly as being the owners of capital. Finally, Althusser (1970) stresses that the dominant ideology is always the ideology of the dominant class. Along this line, we must conclude that an appeal for Justice and Right is an appeal for the reinforcement of the economic laws and the laws that ultimately ensure each of the myriad exclusion factors dealt with as epistemic injustice. In summary, *epistemic injustice is a call for more of what produces it.* This is the reason for its success.

The internalist view of mathematics

Epistemic injustice makes its entrance in sociology of mathematics via Rittberg, Tanswell and Bendegem (2020). Its fruits are surveyed in Kidd, Medina and Pohlhaus (2017). (How many trees had to be cut down to produce the cellulose for this edition?). It makes its entrance in mathematics education via Tanswell and Rittberg (2020), who endorse what they call the *apprenticeship model* of Dawkins and Weber (2017). Let us examine what this model brings into mathematics education.

Dawkins and Weber (2017) strongly advocate for teaching proofs in mathematics classrooms; they do not specify levels: "we maintain that proof instruction – as an apprenticeship in mathematical practice – should not shift away from proving practice itself" (p. 138). They address the recommendation that "enculturating students into classroom proving practice involves an enculturation into mathematicians' values" (p. 126). Clearly, their proposition amounts to aligning the mathematics classroom to the need of reproducing the mathematicians' qualified labor power (Baldino & Cabral, 2020), supported by the internalist view that mathematicians hold on their own practice.

Let us consider the epistemological rationale of Dawkins and Weber (2017). "By *proofs*, we are referring to the written artifacts that mathematicians call proofs" (p. 124). However, they do not say who mathematicians are. From the article, we infer that mathematicians are the members of a community of proof producers. Thus, they start from the circular definition: *proofs are the production of proof producers.* Hegel would say that there is nothing wrong with circular definitions; they may express the result of a dialectical process (Hegel, 1969).

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As written artifacts, proofs are a form of speech. Cabral and Baldino (2021) show that the dialectics of history has generated a community of speech, together with a special form of speech of which proofs are a particular case. They call this community “mathematics” and its members, “mathematicians”. In this sense, the circularity of the expression “mathematics is what mathematicians do”, perfectly expresses the genesis of mathematics. We will see more of this below.

However, in the enunciation of that statement by Dawkins and Weber (2017), the dialectic character of the definition of proof is lost, in favor of a frozen image of proofs as construed by the internalist view of 20th-century mathematics. As spokesmen for the present state of their community, they seek to “conceptualize proof in terms of ‘values and norms’” (p. 124). They need new definitions: “values represent a community’s shared orientations that underlie shared activities” (p. 125) while the term norm “refers to the expectations on practice accepted by the scientific community to uphold a value” (p. 126).

Tanswell and Rittberg (2020) invoke Kant’s philosophy to justify two of their values: “mathematical knowledge is justified by *a priori* arguments” and “mathematical knowledge and justifications should be a-contextual and specifically be independent of time and author” (p. 128). An effort in abstraction is necessary to make sense of these statements.

Let us consider “one plus one equal two”, a mathematical knowledge which certainly the authors would “perceive as being held by the mathematical community” (p. 128). For indigenous populations of Brazil, one plus one may be one, as in the case of a piton and a duck. It may also be zero, if one misses two shots and loses two arrows; or it may be three, as in the case of a father and a mother (Ferreira, 1997). Is this knowledge independent of context? Can it be justified *a priori*? It can only seem so after a great effort of abstraction: we are not talking about ducks and boas. We could ask them: what are you talking about, precisely? They only know that it is something that has norms and values.

However, how did it happen that “one plus one equals two” has become an *a priori* knowledge to common sense? This is what Hegel’s Logic is perceived to explain, but Hegel’s criticism of Kant is precisely what Dawkins and Weber (2017) must ignore to uphold their internalist view of mathematics (Pais, 2016). They do not seem to realize that, ultimately, the adequacy of norms and values to conceptualize proofs must be subjected to the judgement of the same community of proof producers.

As spokesmen for the community, the authors express the difficulty of establishing pedagogic conditions that will put students in the mood of proving, but they do not regret castoffs. For their purpose, it does not matter that only a few students endure enculturation into proof writing, as they are careful not to fail too many. During summative assessment, they always put some easy questions to the majority and one or two difficult quizzes to the “good ones”. This is what their internalist view calls mathematics education.

From injustice to exclusion

In Dawkins and Weber (2017) the words “justice” and “injustice” do not appear. This absence did not keep Tanswell and Rittberg (2020) from choosing this paper to support the entrance

of *epistemic injustice* into mathematics education. They open their case by stating two axioms: “mathematics practices are governed by norms and values” and “classroom mathematics should refer to professional mathematics practices” (p. 1199). They justify these statements with what they call the *apprenticeship model* of mathematics education, which, on page 1201, they erroneously attribute to Dawkins and Weber (2017).

Next, they observe that the norms and values of mathematics practices do not coincide with the cultural background values of students, a difficulty that they call the *research gap* (p. 1199). For ethical reasons, they say, it is necessary to “negotiate and adjust” (p. 1199) these values. For this negotiation, they “introduce *epistemic injustice* as a philosophical framework that helps reveal the ethical imperative to traverse the research gap” (p. 1199); they hope that “epistemic injustice in the mathematics classroom may be avoided” (p. 1200). They point out that the language used in written proofs that students should learn to reproduce may be a source of epistemic injustice, since it is “devoid of many features of natural language” (p. 1202). The authors conclude that “the apprenticeship model is in need of refinement” (p. 1209).

For Tanswell and Rittberg (2020), negotiation is also necessary due to the possible clash between ethical orders stemming from mathematics practice and ethical values present in students’ cultural background. “The ethics we are subject to depends heavily on the role we are currently occupying” (p. 1205). The challenge to negotiating ethical values while seeking to traverse the research gap and avoid epistemic injustice is that “the classroom is a space in which multiple roles and their associated ethical orders are present and may come into conflict” (p. 1206).

Tanswell and Rittberg (2020) argue that “the framework of ethical orders also helps to identify the many roles that are inhabited in the mathematics classroom” (p. 1206). The reader expects that they will not miss two paramount teacher roles: their *tutoring* and their *summative assessment functions*. Summative assessment can put teachers into dramatic ethical dilemmas that Cabral and Baldino (2019a, 2019b) call the *splitting moment*. However, the reader’s expectation is frustrated:

Adopting the framework of ethical orders also helps to identify (...) the array of values, norms and responsibilities these entail. For instance, there are the distinct roles for the student and teacher, which come with very different perspectives, but beyond this they are both engaging with the ethical order of mathematics (Tanswell & Rittberg, p. 1206).

By looking for ethical values and responsibilities in the classroom, these authors are led back to the vague “ethical order of mathematics”. This is astonishing: how is it possible to *look at* a classroom in search of roles that could lead to epistemic injustice and fail to *see* summative assessment?³ The mandatory universal summative assessment practice is the moment when a symbol is written beside the name of each student, meaning that a decision of passing/failing has been taken. This practice materializes epistemic exclusion in school, no matter its euphemistic disguises.

³ “The officer paused with his glance on the space where Aureliano Segundo and Santa Sofia de la Piedad were still seeing José Arcadio Segundo and the latter also realized that the soldier was looking at him without seeing him” (Márquez, 317).

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Summative assessment decides whether each student will get credit for the course, that is, whether she may or may not increase the value of her labor power by adding to it the work done by her, the teacher, and the staff during the course. Value is human labor crystalized in commodities, says Marx (1962). Upon graduating, the student will be the owner of a qualified labor power of higher value, which she expects to sell for a higher salary. Therefore, school is an economic enterprise and failing a course has economic implications (Pais, 2014; Baldino & Cabral, 2015, 2020).

As human work, value is substance and, as such, it does not disappear. In case the student fails, whither will the value already produced by the student go? It will be collected by her colleagues who passed, as a prize for having won a competition. *The work done by all is appropriated by those who pass.* This conclusion of Baldino (1998) is bound to raise objections. However, there is no success without failure. Even if it happens that everybody passes, the mere possibility of failure establishes the perspective of competition. Thus, the truth of epistemic injustice is *economic exclusion*. Epistemic injustice is a feature of the victimization ideology whose aim is to cover up and ensure the permanence of economic exclusion. This explains why Tanswell and Rittberg (2020) must avoid summative assessment when looking for epistemic injustice.

This point where the signified “exclusion” is attached to the signifier “injustice” is what Lacan (1971) calls a *quilting point*, borrowing the name from the mattress industry.⁴ From this point on, Tanswell and Rittberg (2020) may be read back to reveal its political effect. The imposition of the “apprenticeship model” to enculturate students into the mathematicians’ professional proving practice is actually intended to open the “research gap” that allowed the authors to present themselves as *defenders of their own victims*. The “apprenticeship model” assigns to teachers the impossible mission of teaching all students to “write proofs”, under the sole argument that this is what mathematicians do. The qualified labor power of the students who succeed in this mission acquires a high sign value as the prize for winning a competition with so many losers. For these, it is necessary to “negotiate ethical orders” under the constraint of avoiding massive failure in the course. Thereby, *unspoken non-mathematical subsidiary criteria* are introduced into the summative assessment. This is the true ethical question that was kept in the shadows by the “ethics of mathematics”, an abstraction ensuring that economic exclusion remain out of sight at adequate level.

Grounding theory on practice

To say it all at once: we too adopt non-mathematical, economically excluding, summative assessment criteria, but there is nothing in the shadows: *we reward effort to understand, instead of evaluating final learning.* To unfold this aphorism and justify our assessment criteria, we need three definitions, grounded on Lacan’s psychoanalytic theory (Lacan, 1981).

⁴ The quilting point is the stitch that transforms a sack into a cushion.

Evaluating learning or evaluate understanding?

Teaching is to ask questions and return the meaning of her answers to the student. The teacher assumes the position of the demanding Other: *what does he want?*, the student asks herself, an interrogation that Lacan writes in Italian *che vuoi?* to avoid the gender implication. In opposition to “conveying meaning,” teaching is listening and showing understanding of what is heard.

Learning is to represent oneself as a subject by new signifiers. The student assumes the position of speaker and ventures a new representation into the field of the Other, where she must constitute herself as a desiring being. Learning is speaking, in the broad sense, including gestures, hesitations and silences. It is a restructuring of the subject’s *jouissance*. It does not occur *in vitro*. It depends on a myriad of factors such as cultural background, gender, ethnicity, etc. These factors remain at work overnight.

Understanding is the student’s ability to sustain her subjective representation by a signifier. In understanding, student and teacher are publicly interacting in the *agora*. Understanding is an objective process, it can be registered in video; it is a being-there (*Dasein*) and as such *has a measure* (Hegel, 1985, p. 330⁵); thus, at least in principle, understanding can provide a precise ground for summative assessment.

In summary, *one teaches by listening and learns by speaking*. Traditionally, one teaches by showing dominance over knowledge (*séance magistrale*). In this system, summative assessment is designed to give free course to the myriad of cultural biasing factors that work overnight to boost/hamper learning. One may say that this is a true epistemic exclusion of those who somehow have not incorporated (learned) the imponderable values of the ruling class present in the whole summative assessment situation.

To compensate for epistemic exclusion, we seek to develop a reliable way to evaluate the *effort to understand mathematics*. To unfold this statement, we must make precise what we mean by “effort” and by “mathematics”.

What do we call mathematics?

It is useless to ask mathematicians. They do not know what mathematics is; they only say that mathematics is about this and that. They do not know what a proof is, either; they only say that it is “conceptualized in terms of values and norms”. In Cabral and Baldino (2021), we describe the underlying historical process that started in Ancient Greece and has generated a special kind of speech, along with a *community of speech* that upholds it as epistemologically valid. These speeches we call *quilted speeches*.⁶ Inside the community of speech, they came to be called proofs. The essence of a quilted speech is the *attempt to stop the sliding of the signified under the signifier*, that is, the possibility of justifying each inference from one

⁵ *Alles, was da ist, hat ein Maaß*. Alles Daseyn hat ein Größe.

⁶ Quilted speeches emerged in Ancient Greece, together with coinage; they were socially necessary to avoid intrafamily clashes between the economically broken landowner progenitor and his rich brothers who were free to go into commerce. These were indeed very special social circumstances.

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statement to the next by an explicit consensual argument; these inferences are the *quilting points*. The community, with its statute of validity, is what can be properly called mathematics; its members are the mathematicians. An interesting description of the statute of this community, specifying what counts as a valid argument, may be found in Rittberg, Tanswell and Bendegem (2020).

To make clear what we mean by quilted speech, we present an episode of our current freshmen calculus course. The students had received a worksheet with the proof of the derivative of t^2 and had been required to justify each quilting point, represented by the numbered equality signs in the excerpt shown below. In the previous class, they had engaged in a lively discussion about “infinitesimals” and “limits,” based on what they had found in books and online. Is the limit indeed reached? What is the threshold below which a number becomes infinitesimal? In the present class we were evaluating how they would justify the following quilting points.⁷

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &\approx \frac{F(t) - F(t - dt)}{dt} \stackrel{(0)}{\Rightarrow} \frac{t^2 - (t - dt)^2}{\Delta t} \stackrel{(1)}{=} \frac{t^2 - (t^2 - 2t dt + (dt)^2)}{dt} \stackrel{(2)}{=} \\ &= \frac{2t dt - (dt)^2}{dt} \stackrel{(3)}{=} \frac{(2t - dt)dt}{dt} \stackrel{(4)}{=} 2t - dt \stackrel{(5)}{\approx} 2t \stackrel{(6)}{=} f(t) \stackrel{(7)}{=} \frac{dF}{dt} \stackrel{(8)}{=} F'(t) \end{aligned}$$

At quilting point five we received three students’ collaborations in a row (emphasis added):

Antônio: It’s an *infinitesimal*, so it’s only approximating $2t$.

Cesar: You can divide by it and that’s not wrong. It’s not as if I were *dividing by zero*. But here, when I subtract, then it’s like it were *really zero*.

Erick: It’s like Antonio said, we have an infinitesimal number. So, we are practically *creating a limit* there.

We concluded:

Baldino: This whole discussion you’ve been struggling with since the previous class, and which mathematicians struggled with for 200 years, was resolved in 1824, when an important mathematician called Cauchy said this: “on dit que” – or “it is said that”. It is said that the derivative is the name of $2t$. The whole discussion you had was reduced to one name: “derivative” is the name given to $2t$ by *language convention*.⁸

⁷ F and f respectively refer to the totalized and the daily deaths graphs due to COVID19 as popularized by the media; these graphs had been object of previous classes. We started with stereotyped graphs of a disease outbreak that lasted for 60 days. Once the students were able to express the *moving average of deaths based on one day*, we asked them to express this in the case of an endemic disease that lasted 60 years. Using the 4000-times zoom of CorelDraw, the students were naturally led to express the duration of one day as dt , “a little bit of”, as in Thompson (1914).

⁸ See the video in <https://cabraldinos.mat.br/the-grounding-quilted-point-or-mathematics-of-the-20th-century/>. The students authorized the publication of their names.

Point 5 is the grounding quilting point of twentieth century mathematics. It marks the moment when mathematics broke apart from philosophy and started determining its objects by arbitrary definitions solely aiming at the coherence of its global structure of quilting points. Hilbert hoped for absolute coherence of such language conventions. Gödel showed that this was impossible.

Quilted speeches make possible the historical development of the mathematics community and those quilting points make the *minimal units* of proofs. Therefore, *teaching proofs presupposes teaching the function of quilting points*. If students miss this point, they may continue looking for unquilted justifications, like the mathematicians of the past, and errors are bound to come up.

Evaluating effort

In our classroom practice, students are required to individually justify randomly assigned quilting points or sets of quilting points in previously assigned WS, thereby entering into a dialog with the teachers. *How much effort the student made to prepare herself for this moment becomes evident to all*. Close eye-to-eye conversation eliminates questions about the authenticity of answers. No written homework is required.

Studying a WS is an effort that can be demanded from any student of whatever cultural background. Contrary to what happens in evaluation of learning, this form of rewarding happens at the very moment and situation of understanding; there are no imponderable factors working overnight. Insufficient effort may lead to failure, and failure has an unavoidable economical implication. Thus, competition may still be present, but its criteria are explicit and measurable; thanks to systematic video records, grades may be contested by the students. If group heterogeneity becomes evident, it can be dealt with by establishing handicapped subgroups. Of course, we also evaluate learning for our own sake, not as a criterion for promotion. After a certain level of learning is achieved, it is not necessary to distinguish students with grades.

Does our strategy of rewarding effort ensure learning? It certainly ensures a certain network of learning, but this network must be evaluated by longitudinal and comparative mathematics education research. However, such research may reserve unpleasant surprises to those who support evaluating learning instead of effort, as Thompson (1994) showed.

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